
Pilot Interviews Outcome-For Questionnaire Preparation

Q1. Can you describe your firm's BIM experience level (low, moderate, high)? And why do you believe it is at this level?

1. FIRM 1

We started using BIM around five years ago and introduced it slowly. Now most of our projects use BIM, and the cooperation between the departments is much easier. It allows us to depict the conflicts that could happen and warns us on any conflicts in that area, for example between a pipe and a column, or HVAC. It's helpful to connect the departments together and eases the process. I believe within the past few years we have reached a high level in BIM experience because we have another satellite office that mostly works with BIM. It's helpful, and the back and forth becomes much easier.

2. FIRM 2

We have been one of the pioneer consultants in Kuwait to adopt Building Information Modelling since 2010. BIM has become increasingly vital within consultancy firms across the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry, so its experience level is high. Over the years We have invested heavily in BIM technology, tools and processes to align with industry practices, which has helped to reap the benefits of BIM usage in multiple fronts.

3. FIRM 3

Our research into BIM and its applications began in 2011. Once we've gotten a great handle on how to use the process and incorporate it with other programs, tools and technology, we began implementing BIM into our projects in 2016. Currently, our BIM experience level is moderate to high, and is continuing to advance to higher standards. BIM has helped the firm to expand their projects ranging from small scale to large scale as each project is defined with their own parameters and the general rule is to know which load is used for which part of project, whether it's design, model making or creating technical drawings. Furthermore, the firm's knowledge of BIM is not on a unified level as it depends on the employee's range of knowledge in BIM.

4. FIRM 4

The firm's BIM experience level is high. We would consider ourselves very advanced, and we can back that up with sort of our experiences within Kuwait and outside the country as well, and kind of seeing our competitors, and where they are in the market, so we do we are able to stand behind that let's say so we will consider ourselves at a very advanced level. In addition to that, its client's satisfaction reports back on the way we manage, and deliver our projects, and to what kind of quality they are delivered to.

We have qualified the manager's team with different experience, different disciplines, are well educated, have a good knowledge, and certified from good places with approved experience.

We've been working in the environment since 2014, delivering our first Successful BIM project back then. Since then, we've only kind of moved on and advanced, so we built a very experienced team echoing some of what I'm interested in the previous answer, that we've created a separate department to focus only on this area as well.

The company's investment in digital delivery is the natural progression in this area, advancing beyond simple project level BIM.

5. FIRM 5

We boast a high level of experience in BIM, attributed to our talented team. We have a high-quality firm experience model in BIM based on the type of projects we worked on, whether governmental or private, in which we used BIM software.

6. FIRM 6

In more than 14 years, we have reached a high level of experience because it adopted new technologies and fulfilled all the requirements needed for design and construction.

7. FIRM 7

Our firm's BIM experience level is high but can always be better. Initially, our involvement with BIM began with one project at a time. However, the demand has significantly increased, driven by client requirements and government mandates. Many clients now specifically request BIM, and even when they do not, we proactively use BIM to ensure our team retains proficiency. For instance, during a period when clients were not requesting BIM, we continued to employ it on projects to maintain our skill level like in AlQadsia Stadium, the New Egaila Beach Club, and the new airport project with its air traffic control tower.

Currently, we rely predominantly on BIM for most of our projects. However, some projects are still executed using AutoCAD, as city planning cannot be fully realized in BIM, and landscaping remains in 2D. The new airport master plan project exemplifies our extensive use of BIM. This project includes parking facilities, buildings for food preparation to supply airplanes, and various support structures. Additionally, it features a 6-kilometer air force base comprising 150 buildings, making it a mega project. This airport project is the largest BIM project undertaken by us. I believe no other firm, except one another firm—which completed a large BIM project outside Kuwait—has undertaken a larger BIM project than this.

Q2. Can you reflect on the level of BIM knowledge/awareness in your consultancy firm. What are the means used in your firm to enhance your employees' BIM knowledge/awareness?

1. FIRM 1

Since we started, we have sent our employees to different BIM training and courses, some of them online, some live courses. Honestly, they were intrigued at the beginning, but then again it makes the work between the departments much easier. The clients too preferred it as it took less time for completion. Let's say, I finish the design, then send it to the consultant, then they send it to the structural engineer, then HVAC, whatever other departments. BIM makes these steps much easier and faster, with less work, so they enjoyed it."

2. FIRM 2

We have an internal policy of adopting BIM technology in all projects, which helps the team both for visualization and multidisciplinary coordination. The below are the strategies that we commonly employ to enhance their employees BIM knowledge and awareness.

- Training Programs
- Webinars/Seminars
- Peer learning and knowledge sharing
- Centralized knowledge sharing resources and libraries.
- Regular updates to BIM tools
- Management support

3. FIRM 3

We conduct training programs for employees; we experiment with many online tutorials and encourage employees to attend seminars and training sessions. Our primary software for digital design and drawings are ArchiCAD and Revit. Furthermore, we believe that upgrading to newer programs in the market is not always the right course of action as newer is not always better. Thus, we continue with ArchiCAD as it is the more stable software and our knowledge of it is better. BIM is a full team of people that must have a clear line of communication. As BIM is cross compatible with different software, we collaborate with several departments from different offices for different purposes such as structural systems as we don't have a full team in our firm here in Kuwait.

4. FIRM 4

We have huge development setup initiatives to even improve our high-level BIM knowledge. The main initiative is our weekly training session every Tuesday morning. We share a lot of knowledge across digital forms, and we encourage knowledge sharing amongst the teams. Surrounding ourselves and employing experienced people, that can spread that knowledge to their teams. Also, ideally, we structure our team with experienced people, as well as juniors so that they can learn from them throughout the process of the project.

5. FIRM 5

The company prioritizes quality and development in its designs and projects by offering a weekly two-hour training session for all employees. These sessions cover the latest trends and solutions to common problems.

6. FIRM 6

We offer many training programs. The first step is to ask our employees about their knowledge on BIM and their level of experience. So based on that information, we will try to keep them engaged by giving them smaller projects that include the use of BIM where they learn the basics of modeling and representation of projects using BIM. We treat people that lack knowledge on BIM in a very calm manner since it is a free environment in our firm, and they can ask questions if they would like. As you can see training is given properly with respect to BIM and with respect to the experience that the trainees are lacking. We are here to guide them and if they are making good progress, they will be a part of bigger projects and bigger teams as well.

7. FIRM 7

We initiated their BIM journey with a hospital project, bringing in external experts to execute and educate others in BIM methodologies. Subsequently, two individuals remained to carry forward this knowledge. Upon my arrival, I conducted further training sessions. Additionally, We recruited additional personnel, including an individual previously associated with us, now serving as a BIM manager.

There are three primary methods for recruiting new personnel: hiring individuals already proficient in BIM to educate others, providing internal training, or outsourcing. While outsourcing is an option during peak workloads, the preferred approach is internal training. However, achieving uniform proficiency can be challenging due to differences in cognitive approaches.

Q3. Can you reflect on the level of BIM application in your consultancy firm. For what kind of applications BIM is used, especially within the design process?

1. FIRM 1

Schematic design, we still use mood boards and sketches, we don't really need it. However, in the design process, BIM really eases, basically everything. Structure, HVAC, it makes the departments work easier. Even for the client, when we show them live 3D models, its easier for them to visualize their project. Let's say I have a plan, in the same program I can 3D it, cut sections, etc., making it easier instead of moving from program to program.

2. FIRM 2

We use various application tools in the design process. AutoCAD, SketchUp and Rhino are used for creating 2D drawings and 3D models during the concept design phase. Parametric design software such as Grasshopper for Rhino and Dynamo for Revit enables designers to create complex geometric forms and explore design variations based on parametric relationships and algorithms. Autodesk Revit is used by architects, structural and engineering teams to produce design models from schematic to end of detailed design. The infrastructure teams use Autodesk Civil 3D for their design process.

3. FIRM 3

One of the most important factors in deciding which application we use in the design process is risk mediation. As most applications tend to crash with heavy files, the firm chooses the most stable programs. The two most used applications for the design process are ArchiCAD and Revit. Rhino, on the other hand, is used as a 3D tool for visualization. Other formats can also be integrated to the design process for enhancements based on an employee's expertise and proposal to use that format.

4. FIRM 4

We start concept creation with different modeling and analysis programs like Rhino. We are trying to test out this format like 3D MAX and ultra-rendering engine like Enscape and Lumion, but once the concept is reaching an approval sometime using Revit during the concept design depends on the project nature. Once we reach the level of the concept being approved, and we move further developing the schematic phase we start to coordinate with mechanical engineers about the shafts where the placement as per their requirement in the mechanical rooms, we mainly use Revit for production in different versions depending on the project requirement. Then we start to model and coordinate in Revit, after we utilize Revit for coordination, and the clash detection process Revit works for mainly schematic IHC agencies for construction.

In addition to that, in parallel or adjacent to the design process there's other activities that requires visualization, and things like this so there are other applications that are used that are quite typical now in the industry. We're not necessarily using anything more, or extra than most are using which are now Enscape. It is the kind of lead runner in the industry right now due to its compatibility with Revit, and its speed but there's also still 3DS Max, Lumion, and twin motion is now coming in. The new sort of runner in the industry is Unreal Engine, and how you can utilize gaming engine technology for a better immersive experience, so that's kind of the new thing that's that people are exploring, especially the major runners. I've covered the main applications there, that's more or less typical to the industry, but the majority of the firms are set up that way with those but that's a suite of applications that deliver them, the project.

5. FIRM 5

We already applied an advanced BIM application. We use them a lot in the design process such as the schematic design stage, detailed design implementation, and ICE.

6. FIRM 6

In our firm, BIM is used starting from the design process to the construction of the project. The main thing that we are using BIM for is the coordination with respect to different stakeholders, different disciplines and special requirements like lighting or landscaping.

We use all of Autodesk's software for BIM including ArchiCAD and Revit which helps in modeling, extraction of information, and extraction of sheets and quantities. We use other software like Navisworks which is used for coordination purposes between architects and structural engineers. Navisworks combines the architectural model and the structural model and detects the clashes to make it easier to coordinate the work between them. Civil 3D is used by us as well and it takes care of the infrastructure, the site utilities such as the drainage, and the excavations done on the site.

7. FIRM 7

Projects at our firm typically commence with concept designs in Revit, necessitating the continuation of the project within the same software platform. Efforts were made to transition to ArchiCAD due to its superior capacity for managing large projects compared to Revit, which struggles with handling large file sizes. However, despite the recognized advantages of ArchiCAD, the transition did not materialize due to the widespread adoption of Revit within the industry and prevailing market trends.

We use Revit and ArchiCAD.

Q4. Do you think that the use of BIM is **too costly? Or this cost is worth the investment.**

1. FIRM 1

It is worth the investment, of-course. Because we did invest time in learning BIM, however it helped cut down on cost in terms of time as well, because time is money in firms. The time spent on a project has a higher cost. For example, our projects with clients are commercial, so most of them want to finish as soon as possible, so that they can rent the shops, apartments, stores etc. Overall, we cut down on costs a lot by using it. Even if it is something new and you must invest in it at the beginning, in the long run it cut down a lot of time and cost.

2. FIRM 2

BIM is expensive from an initial cost which includes initial costs such as software licenses, training, hardware upgrades, and implementation expenses. However, it's essential to consider these costs in relation to the potential benefits and long-term ROI that BIM offers, thus the investment is worthy.

3. FIRM 3

BIM is certainly expensive, but it comes with many advantages, such as time-saving capabilities, the ability to anticipate future issues or challenges, and easier communication and completion of assignments distributed between teams. We are convinced that the investment is worthwhile due to the great return on investment and the exceptional quality it delivers. BIM can divide the model into hotlinks, allowing for collaborative project distribution among team members up to 100 employees simultaneously. Not many clients request the use of BIM into their projects, but the firm provides this service for large- scaled projects.

4. FIRM 4

There is one Term called ROI (Return on investment), and this is where we measure. In the beginning, it was costly. It will cost software, hardware, training, process hiring specialists, hiring third parties to support, but the return of investment if all of this process is true the team is qualified, and the process takes place, and the team is well trained. The return on investment is very high. It's not the overall life cycle of the process costly, it's less than the traditional process. If it's implemented correctly in the beginning, and it is not only worth the investment, the impact of the investment on the case would be very high. An example on a previous project, during the construction when we finish a coordinated zone or a floor we send it to the site. We don't have any rework, nor any wasted material or any issues in the design. We are saving money, and time, as well as providing drawings of high quality. This is from construction not even from design. If I'm doing this coordination in the office and sending it to the site and everything in the site matches with my drawings, that means saving time, material, money, and quality." The client really needs to understand the value of working in this way, and how it will save them an enormous amount of money at different stages of a project. Mostly, or a lot during construction, but mostly during operation. Also, how having the asset built in a built environment can drastically reduce cost and running off of a project of an asset, which most of the value is. It's actually the client that gains most value out of working in this environment. That's still a huge struggle unfortunately in Kuwait is having clients really understand that which currently they do not. It's a slow burner of a process, but eventually we're definitely a lot further than we were back in 2014.

5. FIRM 5

Cost depends on the project size (small / Mega scale). Sometimes with a request for a small villa it will be costly for the client. However, in our point of view it's worth using BIM because it will save time.

6. FIRM 6

Earlier in our firm, CAD was used to create floor plans and sections and the structural team used to find the clashes which would consume a lot of time and money. The architectural team used to draft sections that would result into being the final drawings of the project. There are many spaces which got skipped and created conflicts with systems like ducts and pipes, which used to cost a lot in the construction phase. Now, we are spending much more time in the design phase and if you compare the overall cost of the design plus construction, I may say it got reduced while using BIM. Design wise, the cost increases a little bit because we are taking all those necessary coordination processes during the design phase itself. Construction wise, if something is not fitting properly on-site, things have to get reconstructed and due to that the cost before using BIM was higher but now those mistakes are reduced which resulted in reducing the cost during the construction phase.

7. FIRM 7

The effective utilization of BIM can potentially halve the required workforce and time for completing tasks, provided it is employed proficiently. However, the primary expenses associated with BIM are the acquisition of computers and licenses, as well as the recruitment of skilled personnel proficient in its use.

BIM's foundation rests on three pillars: people, process, and technology, all of which are essential components for its successful implementation. Therefore, investing in a company experienced in BIM implementation can alleviate these challenges.

Regarding the initial costs, they are indeed significant but represent a long-term investment. Transitioning to BIM involves expenses such as upgrading computer hardware, procuring software licenses, providing training, or hiring individuals proficient in BIM software. Consequently, there is a substantial initial financial outlay for companies in Kuwait seeking to adopt BIM.

Q5. Do you think that the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait requires extreme changes in their **organizational structures? And why?**

1. FIRM 1

No, not really. It is the same process, it moves from one department to the other, it is the same meetings. It is just a matter of speeding up the process and time.

Additional Question: Do you think that BIM implementation eliminated a few job positions?

Not really, because we still need architects and Municipality requires plans. Therefore, we need a draftsman for it. We will still need the architects, engineers, structural/civil, it is just that the work is done easier and more convenient. It benefits the client since they always want the work to be as soon as possible.”

2. FIRM 2

The implementation of Building Information Modeling (BIM) by consultancy firms in Kuwait may indeed require significant changes in their organizational structures, primarily due to the transformative nature of BIM processes and workflows compared to the conventional production and design methodology. Consultancy firms need to realize the full potential of BIM and remain competitive in the rapidly evolving AEC industry landscape.

Here’s why:

- Collaborative BIM Environment
- Cross-Functional Teams
- Digital Transformation
- Standardization and Quality Control
- Training and skill development

3. FIRM 3

We are currently a horizontal office and thus our implementation of BIM does not require extreme changes in our organizational structure. There are clear communication lines between the teams after overcoming their learning curve of the software.

4. FIRM 4

We went through this change very heavily back in 2018, where I was leading at that time. There is definitely a big change, and the culture changes is properly the most important, and the hardest I would say. It’s all about the change in management, and the plans, and how you can bring them in, which is a very tough approach to some degree. We were looking to have a CEO that would really understand the value in the change, and really was one of the driving factors in it. Listen when your CEO tells you if it is in this way or that way you try to change, so that honestly helps. In terms of the biggest change, I think it is culture, but if you are looking for actually the biggest change is structure in terms of the employees’ roles. It is understanding the importance of BIM managers as well as BIM coordinators, but bringing BIM managers into your project teams, and putting them into the levels that they have authority and accountability to be able to steel that project, and apply its delivery in terms of BIM I think is one of the very important requirements that without having them there it will be a struggle and probably it will be tough to do.

5. FIRM 5

It is not necessary to change the organizational structure of the firm since it already provides the required structure such as a dedicated BIM manager. A BIM manager also supervises other specialized departments because better integration and communication between departments and the BIM manager are necessary to ensure seamless adoption.

6. FIRM 6

It was a transition phase every firm goes through and mostly all of them have passed it. Earlier, people used to rely on hand drafting and then they started using CAD and it was challenging for them to start using digital tools and a similar challenge appeared while moving from using CAD to using BIM since people are not well versed with the use of technology. So, the challenging part for firms is to make people have a smooth shift between that phase to this phase. So proper training should be there, guidance should be provided, and a proper setup must be made. So, in our firm we are providing that service as well where the firms want to shift their setup from basic CAD to the BIM. We have training programs that would help people learn more about BIM and have a smooth shift between CAD and BIM. People are the key bone because they provide you with a good team that is willing to learn and explore new things. Training people, making them comfortable using these technologies, setting up the standards, putting things properly and procedures and regulations that we are supposed to follow that would make it easy for a smooth shift from CAD to BIM for any organization.

7. FIRM 7

There is a reorganization underway, but there are still individuals who resist adopting BIM, preferring to maintain traditional methods.

Transitioning to BIM is a significant change and cannot be accomplished alone; external assistance is essential. It's more effective to hire a permanent expert to provide training and restructure the workflow rather than relying on temporary help.

At our firm, the team comprises architects, structural engineers, electrical engineers, and mechanical engineers, with no single person possessing expertise in all these areas. As an architect, I can only offer basic guidance to electrical engineers, but I cannot fully teach them the specifics of their discipline using BIM software. Ideally, we need dedicated coordinators for structural and mechanical aspects, which we currently lack. This comprehensive implementation (Image Above)of BIM is not yet fully realized and will take time to achieve. Additionally, recruiting skilled individuals from other countries is challenging and expensive, with no guarantee of their performance. Some people overlook the fact that internal training is a more sustainable approach.

Q6. Do you think that the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait requires extreme changes in the firm's **organizational culture**? And why?

1. FIRM 1

No, it is the same. The design process is the same, and the hierarchy is the same.

2. FIRM 3

Similarly to the previous answer, we easily adapt to new cultures and prioritize easy communication within the office and between other offices. As the firm is not considered a large office, it can take calculated risks when collaborating with other offices.

3. FIRM 4

Yes, it is not only in the structure, but also the culture of the people. If people's culture didn't change starting from top to bottom from the business point of view, or the director level, or the lead and senior level, if these people's culture didn't change the place would fail on this implementation. But yes, it made a huge change in the firm's structure and people culture.

4. FIRM 5

The firm already has the necessary elements to adopt BIM successfully, so it does not need to change its culture. As well as having trained staff in Revit through comprehensive programs, they foster a mentoring culture in which experienced employees share their expertise in BIM, and they embrace new technologies to facilitate effective BIM adoption.

5. FIRM 7

The adoption of BIM within a firm often boils down to individual philosophies. Some employees support BIM, while others resist it, preferring traditional methods. This divide is not unique to us; it is observed in other firms and across the industry. Regardless of personal preferences, everyone must adapt to BIM, as it has become a standard requirement.

Q7. Do you think that there is enough governmental support to implement BIM in construction projects in Kuwait?

1. FIRM 1

Yes. We are the first firm to receive an electronic permit/license from the Kuwait Municipality, and they were very cooperative and listened to our feedback. Usually, there is a stereotype with the Municipality that they don't listen/support, however they actually are willing to listen if it is something easier to work with, like BIM.

2. FIRM 2

While there may be growing interest and momentum for BIM adoption in construction projects in Kuwait, the level of governmental support is not very productive yet and this can depend on various factors such as policy priorities, resource availability, and stakeholder engagement.

3. FIRM 3

We don't think the governmental aspects of Kuwait fully digested what BIM is as a program. However, the Ministry of Housing could use it to its advantage as the program itself is useful. It can number everything. And if something is wrong you can go on and adjust it and it will automatically update everything else for you. But we suggest that if the government or the ministry should use it correctly, they should not be using it at all as it will render it useless.

4. FIRM 4

No, simple answer no way.

Early this year, I was participating in one of the governmental Kuwaiti events with Autodesk, and the subject of the event was exactly your question. All of them agreed that they are so far from this, and even though they have a lot of tries, some of them are completed, some of them stopped, some of them succeeded, and some of them failed. They overall answered that they are so far from any governmental like a unified approach. This is one of the steps Dr. Mohamed Sadeq, and his team supported by me, and some of our friends are trying to push it in Kuwait to have a unified approach. We are trying to meet some people from the National Assembly of Kuwait, and some people from the ministries, and we are trying to have an overall approach for all the ministries to have it implemented. An example such as Dubai and Egypt now and the rest of the world.

5. FIRM 5

While there is growing governmental support for BIM in Kuwait through initiatives by key agencies, more explicit regulations and encouragement are needed to fully realize its potential across all construction projects.

6. FIRM 6

It's at a very early stage for the Kuwaiti government because not only Kuwait, in many countries only the firms are using BIM and there is no such demand from the government. Nowadays Dubai has shifted to that approach and when they submit the proposal to the government for approval, they need to provide BIM models to understand the actual building with respect to its surroundings, design, regulations and security. In Kuwait it is still at a very basic level, and they are slowly moving towards it. Maybe in the future there will be a kind of regulation where the government will ask to provide the BIM model as well. There are countries while compared to others they are very much advanced such as Singapore, UK, US and now Dubai, so obviously Kuwait will be the next one.

7. FIRM 7

BIM has become a mandatory requirement for government projects in countries such as the USA, UK, Sweden, Qatar, and now Kuwait. These governments will not hire firms that do not use BIM software. As a result, designing with BIM is essential for securing government contracts. The private sector is also gradually recognizing the advantages of BIM and starting to adopt it for their projects.

Q8. Is BIM demanded by clients in Kuwait either in the public or the private sector? And why?

1. FIRM 1

Not necessarily demanded by them, they just want to try to finish easier, and lessen the cost. We started using it in most of our projects, so it is basically a given. When we explain to them that the conflicts BIM highlights at the beginning of the project instead of at the end, they enjoy it since it does the job.

2. FIRM 2

BIM is demanded by most private real estate developers and to some extent by very few public sector clients, but it is still not a mandatory requirement. It's important for clients in both public and private sectors to primarily have an awareness of the BIM usage, benefits, cost-bearings for a project. At the public sector level, government initiatives and policy requiring BIM should be mandated as part of project requirements followed by infrastructure projects involving utilities and other public works. We believe once the government policies are enforced, private sectors shall follow the same.

3. FIRM 3

We use BIM all the time unless the project is very small in scale. But the minute it has the potential to become a real project on a bigger scale they will switch to ArchiCAD (a BIM software).

The usage of BIM or other programs makes no difference to the client, their goals will be met, and using BIM will guarantee less time, and therefore that's the option they go with.

We will use BIM software whether the client demands it or not because it is easier for them to manage and work.

4. FIRM 4

I would not say demanding no, sometimes it is just a requirement. I am saying it is not a demand, because it's not specific and it is not detailed and there is a lot of room for interpretation, and it is not enforced, which is the worst part when you have a consultant like us being onboarded in a project. We come to it with the mindset that this is the way you deliver a project, this is the way we typically work. It's kind of just comes in naturally, but then you have stakeholders in the project that just don't take part and the whole thing just really falls apart, so it is a big struggle. I would say in the last 10 years we see more RFP's (request for proposal) comes in from clients with BIM requirements. It is still not structured in the way it should be. One prime example of a well-structured BIM project is the NEOM that we were involved in KSA. They come through with a very detailed structured BIM requirement on the project, that is sometimes tough to meet in certain areas, but understandable, and easy to follow, and that's the very big missing part here in Kuwait unfortunately.

It is the client that gains most value from working in BIM environment. That's still a huge struggle unfortunately in Kuwait with clients not understanding the value of BIM. It's a slow burner of a process, but eventually we're better than we were back in 2014.

5. FIRM 5

Yes, we agree that BIM is in demand by clients in both the public and private sectors specifically for bigger projects in Kuwait. Due to its benefits in project efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and alignment with international standards, as well as the government's initiatives to modernize the construction sector.

6. FIRM 6

BIM in Kuwait is not that much demanded by clients or the government. Very few clients have this demand because they thought that the client needs drawings, and the drawings need to be given to the contractor and the contractor will execute the project using those drawings. Now some of the clients are demanding the use of BIM because they want to see the BIM model since they understand the benefits. BIM as said is the life cycle of the building, it can be used during construction, demolition, facility management and the operation phase. Firms like ours use BIM because they know the benefits even if clients are not demanding it.

7. FIRM 7

BIM demand has significantly increased, driven by client requirements and government mandates. Many clients now specifically request BIM, and even when they do not, we proactively use BIM to ensure our team retains proficiency. The private sector is also gradually recognizing the advantages of BIM and starting to adopt it for their projects.

Q9. What do you think are the main driving forces for the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait?

1. FIRM 1

Time, cost, even the future, this type of modeling is used. Even when working with international offices, for example, let's say you are a client and you come to me saying you want to work with Norman Foster, and I want you (NAB) to be the local consultant. Most Likely, they are using those programs. What pushes us to use these programs is that we want to work with these international offices and connect with these firms on a global level. We are one of the first firms that began using BIM and people search for more advanced firms.

2. FIRM 2

The main driving forces for the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait include gaining a competitive advantage, meeting client demands, improving efficiency and productivity, enhancing quality assurance, driving innovation, and realizing long-term benefits for the firm. By embracing BIM, consultancy firms can position themselves for success in the rapidly evolving AEC industry landscape.

3. FIRM 3

Using Building Information Modeling will give the best quality in an efficient time, and since those are two of the biggest factors when it comes to clients, it motivates the firms to go with that choice.

4. FIRM 4

Mainly, at this time, it has started to be mandated (required) by a lot of clients. This is one of the things that is happening recently. In most of the new projects it has been mandated. If clients know exactly what they want or not, but in most of new contracts, BIM is mandated. In Saudi Arabia for example, a project like Neom, BIM is mandated with a very well-defined process. Therefore, we as consultants and construction companies, if we don't follow those steps, we cannot acquire new prime projects. This is one of the reasons. The second one is that some companies like my previous company, they understand the values of BIM and they start to mandate it internally without any client mandating for their good. So, they did this for themselves. They worked with BIM because they believe in its value for their construction process and really it was good. We did really a very well-coordinated project and during construction we eliminated 90% of the traditional process issues and struggles.

5. FIRM 5

The main driving force for consultancy firms in Kuwait for BIM implementation could be the cohesive and skilled team who can be highly effective as BIM consultants for project requirements; BIM consultants tailor their approaches and services based on the specific requirements of each project. Other driving forces are project efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and alignment with international standards, as well as following the government's initiatives to modernize the construction sector.

6. FIRM 6

If you are referring to consultancy firms like us, the adoption of technology is the main driving force. Even BIM does not halt; it evolves day by day. Therefore, to keep pace with the ongoing development of BIM, we are continuously engaged in the learning process. We embrace whatever new technologies emerge in the market, familiarize ourselves with the ongoing changes, determine the current best practices, and explore future possibilities. Hence, adoption and learning serve as the key factors in our approach.

7. FIRM 7

Client requirements are the primary driving force behind the use of BIM at our firm. The main impetus for BIM adoption is its mandate by government regulations, ensuring compliance and meeting project specifications.

Q10. What do you think are the **top benefits** of the use of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait?

1. FIRM 1

Time management, easier collaboration between different departments. I'm telling you this because we have various departments within NAB. For example, we have design, structure, civil, HVAC, electrical, even construction supervision. This really helps a lot running everything smoothly.

Additional Questions:

a) Do you think BIM helped reduce mistakes?

Yes, and they helped us find them even faster. Our structural department could probably find a mistake after designing. With the use of Revit or BIM, they can find the mistakes instantly

b) Do you think BIM allowed you to take in more projects?

Not taking a huge capacity at the same time. Let's say you have 10 projects that would be completed in one year using conventional program and not BIM. With BIM, it could be completed within 7 months. Therefore, BIM allows us to take in more projects at the long run.

2. FIRM 2

BIM offers several benefits to consultancy firms in Kuwait, below are the few benefits:

a. Improved Collaboration: BIM facilitates better collaboration among architects, engineers, contractors, and other project stakeholders. By working on a shared digital platform, team members can collaborate in real-time, reducing communication errors and enhancing coordination throughout the project lifecycle.

b. Enhanced Visualization: BIM enables the creation of detailed 3D models that provide stakeholders with a realistic visualization of the project. This enhances communication and understanding of design intent, leading to better-informed decision-making and fewer misunderstandings during the design and construction phases.

c. Efficient Design and Documentation: BIM streamlines the design process by allowing for the creation of intelligent building models that contain detailed information about building components, materials, and systems. This enables consultancy firms to generate accurate drawings, schedules, and specifications more efficiently, reducing the time required for design documentation.

d. Clash Detection and Risk Mitigation: BIM facilitates clash detection, allowing designers to identify and resolve conflicts between building elements before construction begins. This minimizes the risk of costly rework and construction delays, resulting in smoother project delivery and improved project outcomes.

e. Quantification and Cost Estimation: BIM enables accurate quantity take-offs and cost estimations by associating cost data with building components in the model. This helps consultancy firms produce more accurate project budgets and cost forecasts, reducing the risk of cost overruns and ensuring better financial planning.

f. Facilities Management and Maintenance: BIM supports the entire lifecycle of a building, from design and construction to operation and maintenance. Consultancy firms can deliver as-built BIM models to clients, enabling them to efficiently manage and maintain their buildings over time, resulting in reduced operating costs and improved facility performance.

g. Compliance and Regulatory Support: BIM helps consultancy firms ensure compliance with local building codes, regulations, and industry standards. By embedding regulatory requirements into the BIM model, firms can identify compliance issues early in the design process and address them proactively, reducing the risk of costly design changes and project delays.

h. Client Satisfaction: By leveraging the benefits of BIM, consultancy firms can deliver projects more efficiently, with fewer errors and delays, ultimately leading to higher client satisfaction. Clients appreciate the transparency, accuracy, and innovation that BIM brings to the project delivery process, enhancing the firm's reputation and fostering long-term client relationships.

3. FIRM 3

BIM benefits firms by offering better coordination. Having a live model running between all members of the project, seeing the conflicts of each part and errors in real-time, and layering all aspects of the project allows them to adapt quickly identify the mistakes, and fix them immediately. Also, modifications are made easier by having full access to the project and its schedule in a neat manner.

4. FIRM 4

Yes sure, so generally speaking we believe that consultancy firms in Kuwait can benefit from the use of BIM since it fosters collaboration among various stakeholders, including architects, engineers, and contractors thus leading to smoother project coordination amongst different entities. To add on that, the benefit of regulatory compliances that comes with BIM, so it helps ensure compliance with local building regulations and codes (Kuwait Municipality), leading to the reduction of the risk of legal issues during and after construction.

5. FIRM 5

The top benefits of using BIM for consultancy firms in Kuwait include many but most importantly time saving for over 70% throughout the total work life cycle, resolve clashes in the project phase therefore avoiding costly rework. Another benefit is the design accuracy, reducing the likelihood of design errors and omissions.

6. FIRM 6

You can say that better coordination and better design is created using BIM. Nowadays, multiple teams and multiple stakeholders can work together using BIM. So, BIM is helpful for everyone. For example, if we are working on a project and has multiple stakeholders, and if someone is helping us from the UK or US, of course, using these technologies allows them to work with us at the same time on the same file. Multiple people can work simultaneously, so using BIM coordination becomes super easy, and that's the benefit here.

BIM is a very useful tool for communication since it makes the client aware of the team's planning and design. So that the client can easily ask for any alterations in terms of aesthetic or in terms of the layout. BIM is a powerful tool for communication between the designer as an architect or an engineer with the client. Because the client could ask for changes that could affect the design and those changes are not suitable for the design. So, using BIM makes it easy to make the client aware of the mistakes that those changes can cause and what is the best alternative for the alterations that they need in the project.

Design firms like our firm used to design the 2D drawings and send them to contractors which would lead to a set of problems because the drawings were not designed with respect to the 3D environment. So, for example, if the ducts and pipes were drawn in a 2D manner it would cause a problem because of the complexity of each duct and each pipe in terms of its location and where it is supposed to reach. Before using BIM, the work needed to be rechecked and repeated after each phase and alterations needed to be done on site which would cost a lot during the construction phase of projects. After using BIM all of these alterations were solved before the construction of the project and all of the repeated work and clashes would get resolved in the design phase and the contractor would get well-coordinated models, drawings, and reports which would result in reducing the cost.

Many BIM software can help you generate concepts during the schematic design phase of the project. BIM has also impacted the design process in terms of providing a better platform for designers to develop and test materials' alternatives in a 3D manner. All these options can be studied and can be imagined better using BIM software.

If your BIM model is ready with proper materials and it fulfills the design requirement, you can extract the quantities like the cost of the concrete for example, how much concrete is used in the project and from which company I can get the concrete from. So, everything is calculated based on the extraction from the BIM software.

BIM can help in the design process since BIM is cloud based which makes it easier for them to have a look on the design loads, what stage are they at in the project and how much progress they have done, so, everything will be recorded, and it shows where they are with respect to the overall design wise and construction wise.

In terms of project management, BIM will help you with the process of construction as well as giving you details on the amount of time needed to construct one part of the project and it will estimate when it will be done. So, you can compare digital progress with on-site progress.

When it comes to facility management, the same model we used in the design phase extends to the construction phase and beyond. When it reaches facility management, they have a ready 3D model. In this model, they add further information. For example, a table may have been modeled during the design phase, with additional details added during construction. In facility management, all necessary information such as the brand, purchase date, regular maintenance schedule, lifespan, and contact person is included for each entity. This comprehensive data ensures that managers have all the necessary information when conducting inspections or addressing issues. Utilizing BIM in facility management streamlines processes, as illustrated in this example. However, BIM can facilitate many other tasks in facility management, not only in buildings but also in service plants or factories where mechanical equipment and motors are present. BIM can manage information related to maintenance history, service providers, costs, spare parts, and more for such equipment, enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in facility management operations. BIM gives you flexibility as you can choose materials, consider the environmental impact, and select site-wide information such as the site location, sun-path impact, wind flow, and common materials based on the site. So, we have a lot of software and plug-ins. BIM is used for sustainable purposes; it provides analytical reports, like how much heat will be gained because of certain materials or orientation, and so on. Sustainability is one of our branches in the firm.

BIM allows you to envision and simulate a construction environment prior to actual construction. This enables anticipation of all the risks involved, considering factors such as site conditions, construction limitations, and the chosen approach. Questions such as where to position cranes, arrange for loading and unloading, determine building height, and establish safety measures to prevent equipment from falling during construction, can all be addressed during the design phase. Consequently, various simulations can be conducted, visualizing approaches to onsite logistics, including routes for concrete trucks and locations for material handling. BIM facilitates pre-planning by envisioning equipment placement on site and ensuring safety protocols. For instance, in the event of excavation, BIM can suggest the placement of temporary railings or barriers. Additionally, it can designate gathering areas in case of emergencies. In essence, BIM serves as a comprehensive tool for managing safety throughout the construction process.

The cloud in BIM was very helpful in Covid phase so it's easy to work at home, so if you're comfortable with the software that's it you can work anywhere. Multiple people are working on the file, so we weren't out of work, we kept producing even at Covid and all work went smoothly we didn't struggle much.

7. FIRM 7

The benefits of BIM include a significant reduction in both personnel and time required to complete projects. In BIM, 3D modeling allows for instant updates across all drawings when changes are made, such as moving a door, which automatically updates the sections, elevations, and 3D views. This automation saves considerable time compared to AutoCAD, where every modification must be done manually.

BIM's automated systems facilitate calculations, schedules, analysis, clash reports, and detections, and support the export of various file formats. Additionally, BIM offers tools for energy analysis, sheet linking, view management, structural analysis, ramp analysis, alignment, and electrical analysis, enhancing efficiency and accuracy throughout the project lifecycle.

Q11. What do you think are the **major challenges/barriers/risks** (managerial, contextual, technical, financial, legal, contractual ...) behind the use of BIM in Kuwaiti's consultancy firms?

1. FIRM 1

For now, I don't believe there really is a risk. Maybe in the future, it could be a risk because it's something new, and if they did not know how to implement it in real life applications, there could be issues. However, as of right now, it works well. I don't think there will be any risks. Maybe, it is a risk in investment, if you're a small firm it would be expensive at the beginning. It could also be a risk if the employees are not willing to learn it.

2. FIRM 2

Implementing Building Information Modeling (BIM) in Kuwaiti consultancy firms may face several challenges across various dimensions:

a. Managerial Challenges:

- Change Management: Resistance to change among employees who are accustomed to traditional design and construction workflows.
- Leadership Support: Lack of top-down support and commitment to BIM implementation from senior management.
- Skills Gap: Limited availability of professionals with BIM expertise and experience in Kuwait, requiring investment in training and skill development.

b. Contextual Challenges:

- Regulatory Environment: Absence of clear BIM standards, guidelines, and regulatory frameworks in Kuwait, making it challenging to ensure compliance and consistency across projects.
- Industry Culture: Prevailing industry culture and practices that may not prioritize innovation or technology adoption, hindering BIM adoption efforts.
- Client Awareness: Limited client awareness and understanding of BIM benefits and requirements, leading to resistance or reluctance to demand BIM in projects.

c. Technical Challenges:

- Interoperability: Compatibility issues between different BIM software platforms and file formats, complicating data exchange and collaboration among project stakeholders.
- Data Management: Handling large volumes of data generated by BIM models, including version control, data security, and information sharing protocols.
- Hardware and Software Infrastructure: Insufficient IT infrastructure and hardware capabilities to support BIM software requirements, necessitating investment in technology upgrades.

d. Financial Challenges:

- Initial Investment: High upfront costs associated with BIM software licenses, hardware upgrades, training programs, and implementation efforts, posing financial barriers for consultancy firms, especially smaller firms with limited resources.
- Return on Investment (ROI): Challenges in quantifying the financial benefits of BIM adoption and demonstrating ROI to justify investment decisions to stakeholders.

e. Legal and Contractual Challenges:

- Contractual Arrangements: Inadequate contractual frameworks and procurement practices that may not adequately address BIM requirements, responsibilities, and liabilities.
- Intellectual Property Rights: Uncertainty surrounding ownership and management of BIM data and intellectual property rights, leading to legal and contractual disputes.

Addressing these challenges will require a concerted effort from consultancy firms, industry stakeholders, and government authorities in Kuwait. Strategies may include developing BIM standards and guidelines, fostering a culture of innovation and collaboration, investing in training and capacity building, promoting client education and awareness, improving interoperability and data management practices, securing adequate funding and financing mechanisms, and enhancing legal and contractual frameworks to support BIM adoption.

3. FIRM 3

The biggest challenge to a firm that adapts BIM entirely is collaborating on projects. If the other firm uses BIM software, then the project will go smoothly. Otherwise, you cannot go with it due to issues in coordination. Another challenge is the scale, a building will differ in programs to a master plan and the file may not be able to handle it. Along with the challenge of having to connect multiple programs to the file when it comes to master planning. Thus, when it is a bigger project, the project is usually divided into multiple files.

4. FIRM 4

If the place didn't start with the right process, and with the right people, while doing the required training, as well as doing the right process changing and hiring qualified people, then they will fail. I usually say in any seminar/event, if a firm starts implementing BIM and all they have done is buying new hardware and software and then asking employees to start using them, they will fail even if they did a training on the software. They will fail because it is not a matter of hardware or software, yet it is a matter of processes and procedures or work flow steps and who will do what? When? It is a complete process.

Additional Question: Do you face any challenges in Kuwait specifically when you try to implement this type of program or system, is there a specific governmental approach in Kuwait that would make the procedure difficult in terms of legal, financial issues, that pace faced not issues from the firm but from outside factors in Kuwait?

No, nothing like this because if we did the job in house all is good so what's their problem no because if we are using it because we want to use it they don't have the right to say anything but if they are afraid and they don't understand what they are asking for maybe this is the case, so the risk here if you want to define this is the risk the client is asking and they don't know the client what is he asking for.

5. FIRM 5

Some risk factors are that BIM has a high cost of money, time, and manpower, but it is well worth the risk because it provides construction issue mitigation and quickens the detection of any future faults. Another challenge we may face depends on the BIM manager's level of competency, the project may be a success or a failure.

6. FIRM 6

There is no risk here because BIM is not made for any risk or mismanagement; it is completely positive. BIM is designed to work on the challenges during construction and to address any risks that may occur during the post-construction or design phases. It's a virtual environment that we create before executing the project on-site, thus ensuring a positive outcome. However, the only issue arises when clients are unaware of the software's benefits. They may question why we conduct some of the work in BIM. Aside from that, I don't think there are any risks or barriers in using BIM.

The most challenging thing is fitting the right people in certain units, it becomes easier when putting someone to manage that certain unit of people, we would get better results. The second challenge is using the proper Technology (proper software, proper computers). But overall the main challenge is indeed the people, for example some people, old ones usually, who are not familiar with the new architectural software usually are harder to work with so we had to let them be aware of the technology and it takes some time for them to get adapted to this type of technology, and that's the major challenge but most younger architects do know the new software as a result it's easier to work with them.

7. FIRM 7

Design clashes are a significant challenge in BIM, such as ducts intersecting beams or inadequate corridor sizes. These issues can result from human error or limitations in the software and hardware, such as those seen with Revit, regardless of computer power.

The primary risks associated with BIM are technical and include finding and training the right personnel proficient in BIM.

This highlights the foundational elements of BIM: people, process, and technology. Technology encompasses the hardware and software used, the process involves proper modeling and procedures, and people refer to the trained professionals who implement and manage the BIM systems. Ensuring the alignment and proficiency in all three areas is crucial for effective BIM utilization.

Q12. Finally, is there are any other issues you want to address related to our topic and we did not cover in our previous questions?

1. FIRM 1

Not really, so far all we've been seeing is positives. In terms of clients, management, employees, it's much easier. It's the same file that goes to each department.

2. FIRM 2

It's important to address the integration of sustainability and green building principles with BIM. Sustainable design and construction practices are increasingly important in the AEC industry worldwide, driven by concerns about climate change, resource depletion, and environmental impact.

3. FIRM 3

There are no issues, but note that at the end of the day, a tool is a tool, BIM is a tool and if you do not use it the way it is intended to be used it will not be beneficial to the individual or the firm using it.

4. FIRM 4

No, actually yours quite general covering a lot of stuff it needs a governmental implementation, unified approach from up to down from a very up, or a very high level like from the council of ministers or even Al-Diwan Al-Amiri to be implemented in a right and a good way with a well-defined process with government sectors that have the ability to receive for example if they ask for something they know how to receive it and how to review it asking for stuff without knowing how to receive it or review it and the resistance here become scary. Imagine that you go to a fifty or sixty year old architect or engineer all of his life doing his job in a particular way in one day you tell him to forget all of what you have learned and open this model that has everything inside so in this situation he would be shocked, and sometimes there was no support from the administration or the country. In this situation things would go wrong and automatically would fail and they would go backward, and this happens in many places.

5. FIRM 5

Something we would like to add is that while the skill level in Kuwait is high, BIM has a high potential to be more widespread in the future if universities focus on BIM. We also suggest that universities offer more advanced technology for students other than BIM such as 3D laser scanning and point-cloud modeling technology.

6. FIRM 6

You've touched on most topics related to BIM, but regarding new technology, BIM is advancing rapidly. It's no longer tied to individual users; it is now cloud based. This means all your files are managed in the cloud, along with all digital work and information. Working in Kuwait doesn't limit you to Kuwaiti projects. At our firm, we have projects in Saudi Arabia and Dubai, made possible by BIM's online accessibility. Not everyone needs to be proficient in Revit or Navis; these are primarily used by designers, architects, and engineers. However, clients expect to see results. BIM enables showcasing project-related details to clients. Lastly, we utilize ACC (Autodesk Construction Cloud).

7. FIRM 7

There is a wide range of experience and capability levels among BIM users. Some individuals excel with BIM and require minimal assistance, while others, despite years of experience, still need support.

Another significant issue is the scheduling approach. The MacLeamy curve illustrates the distribution of man-hours and effort over time for both AutoCAD and BIM. Unlike AutoCAD, which allocates more effort towards the end of the project, BIM requires substantial effort at the beginning. In Kuwait, project schedules still follow the AutoCAD model (traditional method), which allocates minimal time at the start and extensive time towards the end. This approach is incompatible with BIM, which necessitates a shift to a BIM-centric schedule to effectively manage costs and design changes early in the process, thereby reducing overall costs.

The traditional AutoCAD mentality involves completing the design before involving contractors, who then identify practical issues. This could be avoided by adopting the Integrated Design Process (IDP), where all stakeholders are involved from the project's inception, leading to more efficient outcomes. However, IPD is not yet widely implemented in Kuwait.

Adopting a BIM schedule could reduce construction changes by 80% if used correctly. Despite presenting this concept to the Ministry of Housing and the Ministry of Public Works, it has yet to gain acceptance. Nonetheless, integrating a BIM schedule into design projects would significantly improve efficiency and cost management.